

D3.1 Mapping of relevant existing networks dealing with SFT across Europe

smart**AKIS**
Smart Farming Thematic Network

Document Summary

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Abstract

Smart-AKIS project aims at examining the suitability and use of Smart Farming Technologies (SFT) in EU Agriculture involving farmers, the agricultural machinery industry, academia, research centres, agricultural engineering and public bodies.

The purpose of this document is to identify existing national and European SFT research and innovation structures, platforms, informal or formal networks, working groups in commissions and events. The identified networks and initiatives will be invited to Smart-AKIS networking and dissemination events.

This report is organized in multiples chapters. The first part presents all the networks on Smart Farming Technologies or closely linked to SFT existing across Europe. The second chapter lists all the platforms created on SFT or on agricultural DATA and knowledge exchanges. The last chapter references all the events on SFT.

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1 Introduction

With the common idea to improve environmental, economical, sanitary and social performances of farms, multiple actors are setting up networks, platforms and events about smart farming technologies (SFT). Those initiatives can:

- mobilize different kind of actors :
 - Companies including industries, SMEs, start-ups
 - Public research entities
 - Private research entities
 - Advisors/extension services
 - Farmers
- have various objectives :
 - development of new technologies
 - improvement of existing technologies
 - sharing the use of new technologies
 - evaluating technologies
- be on various field:
 - Reduce the use of pesticides, fertilizers and energy
 - Decrease effects on the environment
 - Achieve safe agri-food chains
 - Facilitate farmers activities

In parallel to Task 1.2 “Inventory of research results” and Task 1.3 “Inventory of industry SFT solutions on the market”, we have identified here existing national and European SFT research and innovation structures, platforms, informal or formal networks, working groups in commissions and events. This task has been built on the already existing mapping of research actors made by the ERA-Net ICT-Agri and will be completed with other networks with farmers, industries, advisory services, Operational Groups, etc.

The identified networks and initiatives will be invited to Smart-AKIS networking and dissemination events. This mapping will help Smart-AKIS partner constituting multi-actor workshops in the 7 Smart-AKIS innovation hubs looking for the joint definition of innovation projects and initiatives. That information will be available online in the Smart-AKIS platform and could be used by any interested stakeholder.

2 Relevant networks on SFT

2.1 European level

2.1.1 ICT AGRI

Name	ICT AGRI 1&2 – ICT and robotics for sustainable agriculture
Website address	http://ict-agri.eu
Type of initiative	Network (ERA Net)
timeframe	2009 – End of 2017
Objectives	<p>ICT-AGRI is funded by the European Commission's ERA-NET scheme under the 7th Framework Programme for Research. The objective of an ERA-NET scheme is to develop and strengthen the European Research Area by facilitating practical initiatives to coordinate regional, national and European research programmes in specific fields.</p> <p>The overall OBJECTIVE of ICT-AGRI is to strengthen the European research within the area of precision farming and to develop a common European research agenda concerning ICT and robotics in agriculture. ICT-AGRI develops international research calls to pool fragmented human and financial resources over the boundaries of the participating countries, in order to improve both the efficiency and the effectiveness of Europe’s research efforts. More specifically the objectives of the ERA-NET ICT-AGRI are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping and analysis of existing research and future needs - Development of instruments and procedures for transnational funding activities - Development of strategic transnational research agenda and programmes - Establishing and maintaining of international collaborations and networks <p>ICT-AGRI will help to coordinate European research in ICT and robotics and develop a common research agenda based on shared priorities. New technologies are rapidly emerging and will be capable of revolutionising farming in the near future. ICT-AGRI is supporting the development and implementation of these new technologies for a competitive, sustainable and environmentally friendly agriculture.</p>
Partners	24 partners are participating in ICT-AGRI across 16 countries (full list here: http://ict-agri.eu/consortium/12479)
Contact	http://ict-agri.eu/contact

2.1.2 FIWARE

Name	FIWARE
Website address	https://www.fiware.org/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>The FIWARE Community is an independent open community whose members are committed to materialise the FIWARE mission, that is: “to build an open sustainable ecosystem around public, royalty-free and implementation-driven software platform standards that will ease the development of new Smart Applications in multiple sectors”. The FIWARE Community is not only formed by contributors to the technology (the FIWARE platform), but also those who contribute in building the FIWARE ecosystem and making it sustainable over time. As such, individuals and organizations committing relevant resources in FIWARE Lab activities or activities of the FIWARE Accelerator, FIWARE mundus or FIWARE iHubs programmes are also considered members of the FIWARE community.</p> <p>Independence in decision making, openness, transparency and meritocracy are the cornerstone and founding principles of the FIWARE Community. An important part of the "FIWARE Culture" is also the proper balance between the individuals who invest their time and effort, the companies that build businesses on FIWARE and the application developers who build and deploy new applications based on FIWARE technologies. The structure of the FIWARE Community encourages all forms of contributions and provides safeguards against losing the balance between the various members of the community.</p>
Partners	Around a thousand SMEs, 22 hubs and 16 accelerators across European
Contact	https://www.fiware.org/contact-us/

2.1.3 AIOTI - Alliance of the Internet of Things Innovation

Name	2.1.3 AIOTI - Alliance of the Internet of Things Innovation
Website address	http://www.aioti.org/workinggroups/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	The Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI) was initiated by the European Commission in 2015, with the aim to strengthen the dialogue and interaction among Internet of Things (IoT) players in Europe, and to contribute to the creation of a dynamic European IoT

	<p>ecosystem to speed up the take up of IoT.</p> <p>Other objectives of the Alliance include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fostering experimentation, replication, and deployment of IoT and supporting convergence and interoperability of IoT standards - gathering evidence on market obstacles for IoT deployment - mapping and bridging global, EU, and member states' IoT innovation activities <p>Working Group 6: Smart Farming and Food Security</p> <p>The Topic of this Working Group refers to IoT scenarios/use cases that allow monitoring and control of the plant and animal products life cycle “from farm to fork”.</p>
Contact	info@aioti.org

2.1.4 CEMA

Name	CEMA - European association representing the Agricultural Machinery industry in Europe
Website address	http://www.cema-agri.org/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>CEMA’s mission is to work towards a balanced legislative and regulatory framework in the EU that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supports the competitiveness of the industry in Europe and - enables the industry to provide smart solutions to help farmers worldwide to grow food affordably and sustainably <p>CEMA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - acts as the face & voice of the industry in Brussels and vis-à-vis international organisations (OECD, FAO, UNIDO) - identifies & addresses the impact of EU regulation - develops common industry positions on relevant issues - promotes a deeper understanding of the farm machinery industry among EU decision-makers, regulators & stakeholders - provides expertise & advice to EU Institutions <p>The European Agricultural Machinery Industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Includes 4,500 manufacturers of agricultural equipment consisting of large multinational as well as numerous small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs); - Has a total turnover of €26 billion and provides employment for 135,000 people directly in the sector and another 125,000 persons indirectly in the distribution and service network; - CEMA manufacturers produce 450 different types of machines ranging from tractors and combine harvesters to plant protection equipment and precision seed drills.
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agoria : (www.agoria.be/)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TARMAKBİR : Türk Tarım Alet ve Makinaları İmalatçıları Birliği (www.tarmakbir.org)
Contact	secretariat@cema-agri.org ; +32 (0)2 706 81 73

2.1.5 AEF - the Agricultural Industry Electronics Foundation

Name	AEF - the Agricultural Industry Electronics Foundation
Website address	http://www.aef-online.org/en/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>Seven international agricultural equipment manufacturers and two associations established the Agricultural Industry Electronics Foundation on the 28th of October 2008. The initiative is an independent, international organisation. As a user platform, it provides resources and know-how for the increased use of electronic and electrical systems in farming.</p> <p>First, the main focus was on areas associated with ISOBUS. But that is now no longer everything. The significance of the AEF in the standardisation of agricultural applications has created additional challenges for the organization. Farm management information systems (FMIS), electric drives, camera systems, high speed ISOBUS and wireless in-field communication have been included as new areas of interest.</p> <p>The AEF is an international platform which is accessible to all interested groups from the field of electrical and electronic systems. It is financed through the membership contribution of both founding members and service charges from general members. More than 170 companies, associations and organisations are already members and actively collaborate within the AEF.</p> <p>The AEF will provide the continuous encouragement and support necessary for introducing guidelines to ISO (International Organization for Standardization) standards in agricultural electrical and electronic systems. More than 170 countries are now represented in the ISO organization.</p>

Partners	Seven international agricultural equipment manufacturers and two associations
Contact	europa@aef-online.org ; +49 69 6603-1813

2.1.6 INTERNET OF FOOD AND FARM 2020

Name	INTERNET OF FOOD AND FARM 2020
Website address	www.iof2020.eu/
Type of initiative	H2020 IOT Project
timeframe	2017-2021
Objectives	<p>The Internet of Food & Farm 2020 (IoF2020) project investigates and fosters a large-scale implementation of Internet of Things (IoT) in the European farming and food sector. With a 30 million budget co-funded by the European Union, the project has the potential to bring a paradigm shift in this domain, by drastically improving productivity and sustainability. It will demonstrate the added value of smart webs of connected objects, that are context-sensitive and can be identified, sensed and controlled remotely in the agri-food sector. The project has started on January 1st 2017 and will run for four years with a 30 million € European contribution and a 35 million € budget.</p> <p>IoT has the potential to be a real game changer in agriculture. Recent initiatives showed the eagerness of the sector to seize the opportunities offered by ICT, network and data-oriented technologies. However, current available applications are still fragmentary and mainly used by a small group of early-adopters.</p> <p>IoF2020 will provide solutions and facilitate the large-scale uptake of IoT, by addressing the organizational and technological challenges the European farming and food sector faces today. IoT can for example be used to optimise the quality of EU meat, while minimising possibilities for fraud by enhancing its transparency and traceability. Another example: In total the EU wine business has the highest share of EU agriculture revenues. To keep up with international competition, for both conventional and organic viticulture, IoT technologies can be used to obtain higher quality and environmental sustainability along with decrease in production cost. Focusing on 19 use cases spread throughout Europe, the project provides solutions to 5 agri-food areas: arable farming, dairy, meat, vegetables and fruits and takes into account their own needs and obstacles.</p> <p>The project will develop innovative IoT solutions by fostering co-creation in iterative improvement cycles focusing on user acceptability and business models to boost technology and market readiness level. End-users being at the heart of IoF2020 model, will participate in assessing and improving the technologies at stake, ensuring they meet the requirements and the expectations of the sector.</p>
Partners	IoF2020 involves all the stakeholders in the food chain: from farmers, cooperatives, equipment and logistic suppliers, food processing companies, to consumer organizations and it includes ICT developers. That project federates 73 partners from 16 countries.

Contact	<p>MSc. Edwin Hecker, Project communication, Schuttelaar & Partners edwin.hecker@schuttelaar-partners.com</p> <p>Dr. George Beers, Project coordination, Wageningen University & Research, George.beers@wur.nl</p>
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2.1.7 VALERIE

Name	VALERIE - VALorising European Research for Innovation in agriculturE and forestry
Website address	http://www.valerie.eu/
Type of initiative	FP7 KBBE Project
timeframe	2014-2018
Objectives	<p>The main aim of the VALERIE research project is to improve the accessibility and availability of new knowledge for innovation in agriculture and forestry. The ultimate OBJECTIVE is for a better flow of information to drive innovation in agriculture and forestry around six VALERIE themes.</p> <p>The key VALERIE activities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working with practitioners in 10 case studies to identify current challenges for sustainability in agriculture and forestry - Extraction of knowledge from European research projects to help meet these challenges - The development of the “ask-Valerie.eu” search engine to improve access to information and knowledge. <p>A key aim of VALERIE is to develop an advanced search engine and repository of structured information that will interactively provide information to farmers, agricultural organisations and researchers. It will do so by providing easy access to knowledge created in EU-research projects and other research. The “ask-VALERIE.eu” search tool will allow users to retrieve relevant and useful information using all available and reliable sources. VALERIE will explore new methods to support question formulation (query articulation), to retrieve information and present meaningful answers.</p>
Partners	The VALERIE consortium consists of 14 partners http://www.valerie.eu/index.php/aboutmenu/about-us
Contact	Project coordinator: Hein ten Berge: hein.tenberge@wur.nl Webmaster: Frits van Evert: frits.vanevert@wur.nl

2.1.8 CIGR - International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering

Name	CGIR - International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering
Website address	http://www.cigr.org/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>The International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering (CIGR, Commission Internationale du Génie Rural) is an international, non-governmental, non-profit organisation consisting of a network of Regional and National Societies of Agricultural Engineering as well as private and public companies and individuals worldwide.</p> <p>CIGR was created by a Constituent Assembly on the occasion of the first International Congress of Agricultural Engineering, held in Liege, Belgium in 1930.</p> <p>The main aims of CIGR are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulate the development of science and technology in the field of Agricultural Engineering - Encourage education, training and mobility of young professionals - Encourage interregional mobility - Facilitate the exchange of research results and technology - Represent the profession at a world-wide level - Work towards the establishment of new associations, both at national and regional level, and to the strengthening of existing ones - Perform any other activity that will help to develop Agricultural Engineering and allied sciences.
Contact	TEL: +81-90-9888-4050 – mail : cigr-gs2014@elam.Kais.kyoto-u.ac.jp

2.1.9 EurAgEng - European Society of Agricultural Engineers

Name	EurAgEng - European Society of Agricultural Engineers
Website address	http://www.eurageng.eu/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	The European Society of Agricultural Engineers (EurAgEng) exists to promote the profession of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering and the people who serve it. The Society is particularly active in Conferences, Special Interest Groups, Publications, Networking and International

	<p>lobbying.</p> <p>EurAgEng has 18 national society member organisations around Europe with a few associated organisations. In all, there are 2300+ individual members that are professional agricultural engineers. Most members are from academia and research organisations, but others come from extension and advisory services, technical journalism and manufacturers. For these members, a prime objective is to ensure that a major conference (500-1200 attendees) is held every year to exchange technical research and development topics and enable networking for members and others.</p> <p>ENGAGE, the Strategic Division of EurAgEng, is a network of co-operating research institutes in the fields of Agricultural, Biosystems and Environmental Engineering. Its aims are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and analyse opportunities for research and development in agricultural, Biosystems and Environmental Engineering to advance agriculture and associated industries - Explain, discuss and promote these opportunities both within EurAgEng in particular and the European Union in general. - Encourage and facilitate co-operation between appropriate engineers and scientists within the European Union and in countries with scientific agreements with the European Union. - Make readily available expert advice in the areas of Agricultural, Biosystems and Environmental Engineering. <p>EurAgEng is the European member of CIGR (International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering), the world wide Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering organisation.</p>
Partners	18 National Societies from around Europe. http://www.eurageng.eu/natsocs
Contact	http://www.eurageng.eu/contact

2.1.10 ENTAM – European Network for Testing of Agricultural Machines

Name	ENTAM – European Network for Testing of Agricultural Machines
Website address	http://www.entam.net
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>ENTAM, the European Network for Testing of Agricultural Machines, is made up of public institutions that co-operate in order to improve their activities in the field of agricultural engineering through common projects and activities.</p> <p>ENTAM guarantees an independent and harmonised international testing system. Regarding the voluntary or compulsory testing in the field of agricultural engineering, ENTAM testing stations assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Performance - Safety - Environmental protection - Animal welfare requirements in animal husbandry.

	According to the ENTAM agreement every testing system is always based on official international standards (ISO, EN, OECD). To reach the aim of a common testing activity the different testing stations belonging to the ENTAM members work for a common system called ENTAM Common Methodology.
Partners	http://www.entam.net/partners.php
Contact	mail: info@entam.com - tel.:+39 06 40860030 - http://www.entam.net/contacts.php

2.1.11 Club of Bologna

Name	Club of Bologna
Website address	http://www.clubofbologna.org/en
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	The Club of Bologna is a free association founded by FederUnacoma under the auspices of CIGR and in close collaboration with FAO, UNIDO and Accademia dei Georgofili, with the goal to convene, almost once a year, the highest international experts on mechanization in order to discuss subjects of a pre-eminent importance for the development of the agricultural machinery sector.
Members	90+ individual experts from around the world http://www.clubofbologna.org/en/members-list.php
Contact	Via FederUnacoma (Italian Agricultural Machinery Manufacturers Federation) Via Venafrò, 5 - 00159 Rome (Italy)

2.1.12 International Society of Precision Agriculture (including ECPA)

Name	International Society of Precision Agriculture
Website address	https://www.ispag.org/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	The International Society of Precision Agriculture (ISPA) is a non-profit professional scientific organization. The mission of ISPA is to advance the science of precision agriculture globally. It regularly organises major International Conferences (ICPA) https://www.ispag.org/icpa including a series in Europe (ECPA) https://www.ispag.org/Events/ECPA (see separate entry under ECPA – UK).
Members	Individual members from around the world.
Contact	https://www.ispag.org/contact_us

2.1.13 European Confederation of Agronomists Associations (CEDIA)

Name	European Confederation of Agronomists Associations - CEDIA
Website address	http://www.cedia.eu/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	This body brings together under one umbrella the representative organisations and associations of agronomists from several European countries. It is the European representative body of national associations of agronomists.
Members	Our individual members are graduates in Agricultural sciences / engineering.
Contacts including for member bodies	http://www.cedia.eu/en/contact/index.htm

2.1.14 European Conservation Agriculture Federation (ECAAF)

Name	European Conservation Agriculture Federation - ECAAF
Website address	http://www.ecaf.org/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	ECAAF is a non-profit making international association. It was conceived to encourage any issue focused on maintaining the agrarian soil and its biodiversity in the context of sustainable agriculture.
Members	ECAAF brings together fourteen national associations which promote among Europe's farmers the soil management "best practice" aspects of Conservation Agriculture. With member associations in Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Moldova, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland and United Kingdom, ECAAF represents the interests of the majority of the European Union's cropped farmland.
Contacts including for member bodies	http://www.ecaf.org/about-us/ecaf

2.1.15 Agricultural Industry Electronics Foundation (AEF)

Name	Agricultural Industry Electronics Foundation (AEF)
Website address	http://www.aef-online.org/
Type of initiative	Network – technical standards and validation
Objectives	<p>The AEF wishes to provide the necessary resources and appropriate know-how so that important technical challenges concerning electronic and electrical systems in agricultural technology and farming can be jointly addressed by the industry.</p> <p>Initially, a succession of important tasks associated with ISOBUS formed the main focus of their work. But now the agricultural industry no longer sees the potential of AEF as limited only to ISOBUS. Their work is therefore being expanded to include other important areas such as electric drives, camera systems, farm management information systems, high speed ISOBUS and wireless in-field communication.</p>
Members	200+ manufacturers and organisations
Contact (for Europe)	http://www.aef-online.org/en/contact.html Dr. Philipp Fuchsenberger VDMA (German Engineering Federation) PO Box 71 08 64, 60498 Frankfurt/Main, Germany Tel. +49 69 6603-1813

2.1.16 AHDB PF-Hort Project

Name	AHDB PF-Hort Project
Website address	https://horticulture.ahdb.org.uk/project/soils-programme-precision-farming-technologies-drive-sustainable-intensification
Type of initiative	Research and network
Objectives	The levy board for horticulture (AHDB Horticulture) is funding this project to investigate precision farming technologies to drive sustainable intensification in horticulture cropping systems (the 'PF-Hort' project). The project is led by ADAS and includes field demonstrations of precision farming techniques such as variable rate N applications to brassica vegetables, use of controlled traffic farming (CTF) and techniques for assessing soil and crop variability.
Members	https://horticulture.ahdb.org.uk/programme-workconsortium
Contact (for Europe)	Dr Lizzie Sagoo, RSK ADAS Ltd, Boxworth, Cambs, CB23 4NN; UK. lizzie.sagoo@adas.co.uk

2.2 National level

2.2.1 France

RMT AGROETICA – Agricultural Equipment and Information and Communication Technologies for Agro-ecology (<http://www.rmt-agroetica.com/>)

RMT AGROETICA

Name	RMT AGROETICA – Agricultural Equipment and Information and Communication Technologies for Agro-ecology
Website address	www.rmt-agroetica.com
Type of initiative	Network
Timeframe	2015 - 2019
Objectives	<p>The RMT AgroETICA aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the state of knowledge of the agricultural world on the impacts of agricultural equipment on construction sites including the increased use of new technologies. - Develop a state of knowledge on the subject of the use and impact of new technologies of agricultural equipment on construction sites, including those using the simplified cultivation techniques and mechanical weeding. - Propose for thought on the development of materials (design of new tools (including self-build), integration of new sensors based on optical tools, etc. - Promote the emergence of joint projects on the missing references, methodologies, technical tools, repositories and shared documents. - Promote the results of the various players and the results of collective work of national interest lines within the RMT. It is also to integrate the results of work communication lines outside France and transposed to the national situation.
Partners	ARVALIS, ACTA, EPLEFPA Castelnaudary, FNEDT, FRCUMA West AXEMA, AgroSup Dijon, SEDIMA, EPLEFPA Vesoul, CRA Bretagne, IFVV, Farmer Workshop
Contact	contact@rmt-agroetica.com

UMT CAPTE

Name	UMT CAPTE - Capteurs et télédetection
Type of initiative	Research network
Timeframe	2012 - 2017

Objectives	<p>The Joint Technological Unit CAPTE (Sensors and Remote Sensing to characterize the condition and running of major crops) brings together researchers, engineers and technicians as well as INRA and ARVALIS. The purpose of the UMT CAPTE is to develop acquisition tools and methods of use of observations from the micro-plot (10 m²) scale to the crop field (about 10 ha) scale, to contribute to the three main levers for improving the efficiency of arable crops:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plant breeding, through broadband phenotyping - Experimentation about cropping systems - Pilot tools for crops in agricultural fields distributed on a territory. <p>The UMT tests, adapts and eventually develops sensors on different vectors (fixed for continuous measurements, pedestrian, tractor, drone, aircraft, satellite), integrating the whole chain from its measure to its use in various applications. These sensors record data relating to plant cover, soil and climate. The approach relies on a privileged way on modelling (radiative transfer, structure-function relationships within the plant cover).</p>
Partners	Arvalis - Institut du Végétal, INRA, UMR EMMAH, ACTA, TERRESINOVIA, ITB
Contact	Benoît de Solan – Arvalis - benoit.desolan@avignon.inra.fr

UMT ECOTECH VITI

Name	UMT ECOTECH VITI
Website address	https://itap.irstea.fr/?p=6696
Type of initiative	Research network
Timeframe	2012-2017
Objectives	<p>This Joint Technological Unit aims to reduce the pesticide use in viticulture. The work program aims to reduce the dependence on wine farms to pesticides and focuses on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of decision systems in conventional and organic viticulture to optimize pesticide use - Evaluation of innovative technologies to help the farmer to optimize and secure the plant protection at different scales, - Develop (initial and vocational) training and communicate in the field of innovative application plants protection products technologies to reduce pesticide use.
Partners	IFV, IRSTEA, Montpellier SUPAGRO
Contact	Sébastien Codis, IFV - sebastien.codis@vignevin.com

AgroTIC: The new digital farming chair

Name	AgroTIC - The new digital farming chair
Website address	-
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>Acting as a bridge between research and economics, industry chairs are partnerships between teaching institutions and their socioeconomic counterparts. They take the lead in working on areas of common interest and creating research, training and knowledge transfers.</p> <p>Thus, the primary aim of the new AgroTIC chair is to encourage the distribution of digital technologies for agriculture, particularly by strengthening training-research-industry links. Based on industry needs, 3 lines of research and a relevant action plan have been drawn up in order to develop the sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor digital transitions (research, usage, other sectors) - Explore the possibilities offered by emerging technologies - Identify skills to create new partnerships <p>Based across 2 regions, Occitanie and Nouvelle Aquitaine, the chair already has European ambitions and expects to benefit from international scientific networks to participate in developing technologies and uses for digital agriculture across Europe. Stay tuned for more on the chair.</p>
Partners	<p>A total of 23 companies and technical partners, 3 teaching and research institutions and 1 foundation have come together to launch the AgroTIC industry chair.</p> <p>http://www.irstea.fr/en/all-news/institute/digital-farming-launching-new-agrotic-industry-chair</p>

#DIGITAG – CONVERGENCE INSTITUTE

Name	#DIGITAG – CONVERGENCE INSTITUTE
Website address	http://www.hdigitag.fr/
Type of initiative	Research network
Timeframe	2016 - 2022
Objectives	<p>The convergence Institute on digital farming (#DIGITAG) is led by IRSTEA and supported by the city of Montpellier. #DigitAg is an interdisciplinary research project focused on promotion of digital agriculture and higher education. Some of the AgroTIC chair's activities will also be directly linked to it.</p> <p>The program work will be developed upon 6 topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and communication technologies and rural context

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TIC and innovation - Sensor and DATA collection and management - Information system - Farming Big data structure - Modelling and simulation
Partners	4 research institutes, 4 higher education establishments, SATT AxLR, ACTA, pôle de compétitivité Qualimed et 8 private companies
Contact	contact@hdigitag.fr

CUMA - Le réseau des Coopératives d'Utilisation de Matériel Agricole

Name	Le réseau des Coopératives d'Utilisation de Matériel Agricole
Website address	http://www.cuma.fr/
Type of initiative	Cooperative Network
Objectives	<p>CUMA are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service co-operatives in a agriculture. - Set up by and for farmers - Collective investment and joint use of machinery, building, workers for tasks directly linked to production cycles <p>Little autonomous groups to ease or improve production conditions and increase the farm's productivity.</p>
Partners	12 260 Cuma in France
Contact	france@cuma.fr

2.2.2 United Kingdom

Harper Adams University: National Centre for Precision Farming (Agricultural Engineering Innov. Centre)

Name	Harper Adams University: National Centre for Precision Farming at Agricultural Engineering Innovation Centre
Website address	http://www.harper-adams.ac.uk/initiatives/national-centre-precision-farming/ http://www.harper-adams.ac.uk/facilities/engineering-innovation-centre.cfm
Type of initiative	Research network
Objectives	The National Centre for Precision Farming (NCPF) aims to provide information and a range of support initiatives that will enable visitors to the site to gain an on-going understanding of precision farming, insight into precision farming developments and support services designed to assist farmers and associated stakeholders in applying precision farming methods.
Contacts	http://www.harper-adams.ac.uk/initiatives/national-centre-precision-farming/contacts.cfm

Agri-Tech East

Name	Agri-Tech East
Website address	http://www.agritech-east.co.uk/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	Agri-Tech East is an independent, business-focussed cluster organisation, to improve the international competitiveness and sustainability of plant-based agriculture and horticulture. It is bringing together farmers and growers with scientists, technologists and entrepreneurs to create a global innovation hub in agri-tech.
Contacts	http://www.agritech-east.co.uk/contact/ Agri-Tech East, Hauser Forum, 3 Charles Babbage Road, Cambridge CB3 0GT info@agritech-east.co.uk Tel +44(0)1223 760135

Smart Agri-Systems Platform - CTF Europe (at Soil & Water Management Centre)

Name	CTF Europe
Website address	http://www.smartagriplatform.com/Controlled-Traffic-Farming
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	<p>The Smart Agri-Systems Platform is a membership organisation which helps and supports growers and those in associated industries with information on soils, precision farming (including controlled traffic) and the latest research findings on related topics.</p> <p>This platform also aims to raise awareness of topics being researched by PhD students around the world through video interviews and short articles.</p>
Contacts	CTF Europe contacts in UK and Denmark http://www.smartagriplatform.com/Contact-us Tim Chamen: +44 1525 405121 Email: tim@ctfeurope.eu

AHDB Precision Technology Theme Activity Group

Name	AHDB Precision Technology Theme Activity Group – <i>Driving Technology into Practice</i>
Website address	https://cereals.ahdb.org.uk/regions.aspx
Type of initiative	Network (being established)
Objectives	<p>This Theme Activity Group is being established. It aims to ensure that appropriate research on Precision Technology is undertaken</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to meet farmers' needs but - not duplicate efforts elsewhere.
Contacts	Harry Henderson, Knowledge Exchange Manager East Midlands harry.henderson@ahdb.org.uk

The Agricultural Engineering Precision Innovation Centre (Agri-EPI Centre)

Name	The Agricultural Engineering Precision Innovation Centre – Agri-EPI Centre
Website address	https://www.agri-epicentre.com/
Type of initiative	Research and demonstration network
Objectives	<p>Driving growth and supporting innovative ideas to help farmers and business owners become more profitable and sustainable. The Agri-EPI Centre delivers research, development, demonstration and training on precision agriculture and engineering for the livestock, arable, horticulture and aquaculture sectors.</p> <p>Agri-EPI work focuses on Innovation Hubs and Farm and Processing Centres which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer one-stop access to leading academic institutions - Develop exciting new facilities for research and development, demonstration and training - Initiate ‘Think Tanks’ to coordinate R&D agenda - Partner researchers, industry & funding - Develop business incubation facilities at a range of scales - Provide data for identification of issues/opportunities - Design, test & demonstrate new technologies in real farm/processing situations <p>Agri-EPI Centre is one of four AgriTech Innovation Centres established by the UK government, It is owned by three Higher Education Institutions and three companies from across the agri-food industry. This consortium of key organisations in the field of precision agriculture and engineering brings together expertise in research and industry, as well as data gathering capacity in all areas of farming.</p> <p>The core partners in the Centre are Scotland’s Rural College (SRUC), Harper Adams University, Cranfield University, Harbro Ltd, Ag Space Agriculture Ltd, Kingshay Farming and AGGO Ltd. A further 69 companies are supporting the Centre, including large supermarkets, food producers, farmers, processors and engineering and technology businesses.</p> <p>Amidst the new revolution in information technologies and engineering science, the Centre will explore how to optimise the performance of the highly complex production and processing systems in agriculture. This will include key drivers of profitability and sustainability, such as livestock and plant growth rates, nutrient efficiency, product quality, and health.</p> <p>Initial areas of interest will include cutting edge technologies such as automated vehicles, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs or “drones”), new instrumentation to monitor both operations and in-field performance of cropping systems, as well as sensing and imaging technologies to monitor livestock production in areas such as product quality and health.</p>
Contacts	https://www.agri-epicentre.com/contact-us/

2.2.3 Greece

GAIA EPICHEIREIN

Name	GAIA EPICHEIREIN – Farmers’ service centres (FSC)
Objectives	<p>In order to address the needs of every farmer throughout Greece, GAIA EPICHEIREIN has created a nationwide network of 92 Farmers Service Centers (FSC).</p> <p>The FSCs are located at the premises of the Agricultural Cooperatives that collaborate with GAIA EPICHEIREIN. They represent the main available supporting structure for Greek farmers and their organizations, allowing for easy and direct access to innovative services. The FSCs have been certified by TUV AUSTRIA HELLAS in order to fully meet the requirements of the international ISO 27001 standard: 2005 and are staffed with experienced and qualified personnel.</p> <p>The services provided cover the following categories of agricultural entrepreneurship:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GAIA MANAGEMENT (Management and Financial Follow-Up Services/Tools) - GAIA SUBSIDY (Subsidy and Public Regulatory Obligations Services) - GAIA INFARM (Agricultural Production and Intelligent Agriculture Services) - GAIA COMMERCE (Agricultural Products Trade and Promotion Services) - GAIA SOCIETY (Online Agricultural Society) <p>By using the GAIA EPICHEIREIN services, the private sector of agriculture and especially farmers or generally those employed in the agricultural field, obtain the comparative advantage that makes them stand out.</p> <p>By using the services, Greek producers profit and benefit from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - spending less time on bureaucratic and counterproductive issues - the streamlining of bureaucratic procedures - improving their relations with the Association they belong - the transparency and the prices they are charged for - the technical knowledge for the improvement of their production
Contact	https://www.c-gaia.gr/en/fsc-network

AGROKNOW Services

Name	AGROKNOW Services
Objectives	<p>AGROKNOW helps organisations to build platforms using open agricultural and food data. AGROKNOW can help develop an open data strategy by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defining a data strategy - Identifying open data policies and comply to them - Positioning data-powered services on the agriculture and food ecosystem <p>This can be done by designing and building open data services by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Move from users challenges to applications requirements - Select appropriate open source tools and technologies - Apply data interoperability standards - Select relevant open data sources - Specify data management workflows
Contact	http://www.agroknow.com/agroknow/contact

2.2.4 Serbia

PA4ALL - Precision Agriculture Living Lab

Name	PA4ALL - Precision Agriculture Living Lab
Objectives	<p>Precision Agriculture Living Lab, or PA4ALL, was established in 2012 at BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad. PA4ALL is the first Living Lab (LL) established in Serbia and one of the few in the wider West Balkans Region (WBR) and active in a “niche” field, Precision Agriculture. PA4ALL emerged as a result of the long-term, continuous cooperation between BioSense and the local stakeholders of the Vojvodina region, namely: Innovative ICT SMEs; end users, farmers and agricultural enterprises; and the regional government. Vojvodina demonstrates a particularly strong both agricultural and ICT sector, as well as a dynamic value-chain of stakeholders making the region an ideal test bed for applying the LL approach, hence to produce "Value for Money" innovation.</p>
Contact	Milica Trajkovic - trajkovic.milica.ns@gmail.com

VOJVODINA - ICT Cluster

Name	VOJVODINA - ICT Cluster
Objectives	Vojvodina ICT Cluster provides a single point of contact with the best ICT companies in Serbia. The cluster gathers companies from the sector with the total workforce of more than 2,000 experienced IT professionals. The association enjoys strong support in the community, with five institutions from the areas of education, regional development and public service being honorary members. Founded through a bottom-up initiative in 2010, this cluster is the strongest in its field in Serbia today, with member companies who have numerous references among globally recognizable clients. The mission of Vojvodina ICT Cluster includes coordination of its and its partners' efforts toward a strong positive influence on social and business environment. To its members, the cluster serves as a platform for cooperation and provides a portfolio of services, such as building capacities and competitiveness of its members through participation in project activities, training and education at the Cluster Academy, building links with the education system, creation of new business opportunities, access to new markets, lobbying activities, etc. The cluster also has an important role in building tighter bonds in the triple helix Business-Education-Government.
Contact	Dr. Mladen Radisic - mladen.voict@gmail.com

2.2.5 Netherlands

H-WodKa

Name	H-WodKa
Website address	http://hwodka.nl/
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	HWODKA is founded by a group of innovative farmers with the goal to improve vitality of arable farming, also stimulate nature, landscape and biodiversity. SFT is an important instrument to reach these goals.
Contact	info@hwodka.nl

2.2.6 Spain

Spanish organization on conservation agriculture

Name	Spanish organization on conservation agriculture
Website address	www.agriculturadeconservacion.org
Type of initiative	Network
Objectives	The Spanish organization on conservation agriculture was founded in 1995 as a non-profit and independent entity, open to any person (farmers, technicians, researchers) or legal entity

	<p>(companies, public bodies) interested in promoting agricultural practices which lead to better conservation of agricultural land and its biodiversity.</p> <p>The purposes of the entity are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote information to farmers, agricultural technicians and society in general of the techniques that make it possible to conserve agricultural soil and its biodiversity in the context of sustainable agriculture. - Foster the development, teaching and research of any aspect related to conservation agriculture and biodiversity of the agricultural land.
Contact	<p>http://www.agriculturadeconservacion.org/contacto.html ; +34 957 42 20 99 / 957 42 21 68</p>

FOODTECH NAVARRA

Name	Foodtech Navarra
Website address	<p>http://www.cein.es/crea-tu-empresa/foodtech-navarra/</p>
Type of initiative	<p>Network – funding programme</p>
Objectives	<p>Foodtech Navarra is a program which aims to stimulate the food chain ecosystem in Navarra, promoting, detecting and supporting the launch of new business activity, with special emphasis on technology and / or hybridization.</p>
Contact	<p>administracion@cein.es; 848 426000</p>

3 Other relevant thematic networks

3.1 4D4F: Data Dairy Driven Decision

Name	4D4F: Data Dairy Driven Decision
Website address	http://www.4d4f.eu/
Type of initiative	H2020 Thematic Network
timeframe	2016 - 2019
Objectives	The Data Driven Dairy Decisions for Farmers (4D4F) thematic network will focus on the role which dairy animal and environmental sensors can play in collecting real time information to help make more informed decisions in dairy farming. The network will develop a Community of Practice (COP) comprised of farmers, farm advisors, technology suppliers, knowledge exchange professionals and researchers who will work together to debate, collect and communicate best practice drawn from innovative farmers, industry and the research community to facilitate the co-creation of best practice.
Partners	16 partners across Europe are constituting this thematic network http://www.4d4f.eu/content/partners
Contact	info@4D4F.eu (http://www.4d4f.eu/content/contact-information)

3.2 AGRISPIN

Name	AGRISPIN
Website address	http://agrispin.eu
Type of initiative	H2020 Thematic Network
timeframe	The AgriSpin project will examine the practice of innovation today by answering questions such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does the European farmer seek information and support? - What competencies does he expect of his adviser?

	<p>- What kind of support system is in place today?</p> <p>By doing so, AgriSpin intends to uncover best cases for innovation and identify the type of innovation support system that makes for the most optimal innovation process.</p>
Objectives	2015 – 2018
Partners	To ensure that the knowledge accumulated in the project is disseminated to as many stakeholders as possible, AgriSpin will work towards creating a powerful European network among advisers, researchers, organisational experts and innovation companies.
Contact	Project Manager Heidi Hundrup Rasmussen: hhr@seges.dk (http://agrispin.eu/contact/)

3.3 FERTINNOWA

FERTINNOWA

Name	Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable WATER use in FERTigated crops
Website address	www.fertinnowa.com
Type of initiative	H2020 Thematic Network
timeframe	2016 - 2019
Objectives	<p>The main objective of the FERTINNOWA thematic network is to create a meta-knowledge database of innovative technologies and practices for the fertigation of horticultural crops. FERTINNOWA will also build a knowledge exchange platform to evaluate existing and novel technologies (innovation potential, synergies, gaps, barriers) for fertigated crops and ensure wide dissemination to all stakeholders involved of the most promising technologies and best practices.</p> <p>A multi-actor integrated approach will be used through the FERTINNOWA platform which will involve various stakeholders (researchers, growers, policy-makers, industry, environmental groups etc.) at several levels including the socio-economic and regulatory level (national and European) with a special focus on the EU Water Framework Directive and Nitrate Directive. Information will be gathered at national level to feed a European benchmark study that will evaluate and compare existing technologies used at various horticulture sectors, including vegetables, fruit and ornamentals in different climate zones.</p> <p>All tools, databases and other resources generated will be shared within the consortium and the stakeholders’ group and will be made available to the broader scientific community, policy-makers, the industry and the public at large. FERTINNOWA will help the growers to implement innovative technologies in order to optimize water and nutrient use efficiency thus reducing the environmental impact.</p>
Partners	http://www.fertinnowa.com/project/consortium-members/
Contact	Project managers : raf.de.vis@proefstation.be ; Els.berckmoes@proefstation.be

3.4 OK-Net ARABLE

Name	OK-Net ARABLE
Website address	http://www.ok-net-arable.eu
Type of initiative	H2020 Thematic network
timeframe	From 03-2015 to 02-2018
Objectives	<p>The complexity of organic farming requires farmers to have a very high level of knowledge and skills. But exchange on organic farming techniques remains limited. OK-Net Arable promotes exchange of knowledge among farmers, farm advisers and scientists with the aim to increase productivity and quality in organic arable cropping all over Europe</p> <p>OK-Net Arable takes a very innovative approach in that in all stages of the project, farmers play a prominent role. Much more than being asked for advice, farmers contribute to a process of co-creation of knowledge throughout the project. This work is facilitated by the participation of 14 farmer innovation groups.</p> <p>Knowledge exchange for better farming: Despite substantial growth of organic farming in the EU over the last decade, concerns have been raised whether organic farming is productive enough compared to conventional farming. On the other hand, evidence shows that the more experienced an organic farmer is, the smaller the yield difference with conventional farms. Indeed, organic agriculture works as a complex system which requires a very high level of knowledge. By promoting co-creation and exchange of knowledge, the OK-Net Arable project therefore has significant potential to increase productivity and quality in organic farming.</p>
Partners	17 partners from 12 countries all over Europe (http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/index.php/project-partners)
Contact	Dr. Bram Moeskops, IFOAM EU, bram.moeskops@ifoam-eu.org , + 32 (0) 2 416 27 61

4 Operational groups (EIP-AGRI)

4.1 France

4.1.1 Slopped vineyard

Name	Slopped vineyard
Objectives	The main purpose of this operation is to evaluate the technical and economic feasibility of the "banquette" earthwork in order to mechanize grass destruction in substitution of chemical herbicides. This type of earthwork has to favour mechanization, without destructing landscape, and preventing from erosion. Several soil management systems are studied, between and under wine range (bio-herbicides, mulch, biodegradable mulch, etc.), but also bank maintenance. To allow range mechanization, an intercept prototype will be produced for these particular conditions.
Localisation	Pyrénées-Orientales - France
Duration	from 2015 to 2018
Partners	Chambre d'Agriculture des Pyrénées-Orientales, GDA Cru banyuls et des alberes, CGC Agri
Contact	j.thiery@pyrenees-orientales.chambagri.fr , +33671571965

4.1.2 Optimization of tillage in organic viticulture to reduce production costs and fuel consumption

Name	Optimization of tillage in organic viticulture to reduce production costs and fuel consumption
Objectives	<p>The outputs of this project are for all winemakers wanting to reduce their consumption of herbicides while controlling the consumption of fuels and the production costs. These outputs will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - establish a fuel consumption range of different tillage tools depending on the conditions of intervention - offer to winegrowers different strategies of tillage in a given context of soil, depending on tools available on the winery. <p>Results from this program will enable winegrowers already practicing tillage to optimize their operations and promote the transition to tillage for growers who use herbicides to reduce their consumption. Technical references acquired in this project will secure the tillage strategies.</p>
Localisation	Hérault - France
Duration	from 2016 to 2019
Partners	SUDVINBIO, Chambre d'Agriculture d'Hérault, COLIN CUMA, IFVV
Contact	nicolas.constant@sudvinbio.com , +33 6 63 39 25 02

4.1.3 Captrap Arbo

Name	Captrap Arbo
Objectives	Monitoring in orchards Lepidoptera population dynamics is the basis of the struggles of reasoning strategies. Currently this monitoring is made with traps whose statements are at best weekly by an operator. The project objective is to participate in the adaptation of an

	automatic trap for the main pests of fruit trees. Traps readings will be transmitted by radio (SigFox) and made available on an Internet platform. Work on 3 Lepidoptera: Codling moth, Oriental fruit moth and codling chestnut. A comparison of the automatic trap with the reference traps is being done. Study of the beat frequency of specific wings of each species is also executed.
Localisation	Hérault – France
Duration	from 2016 to 2018
Partners	CEHM, Cap 2020, SERFEL, CRA Languedoc Roussillon, CA Pyrénées orientales, Cofruidoc
Contact	xcrete@cehm.net , +33 4 67 71 55 00

4.1.4 Zero herbicides in Mediterranean perennial crops

Name	Captrap Arbo
Objectives	The project “Zero herbicides in Mediterranean perennial crops” aims to evaluate and promote innovative weed management techniques without herbicides in perennial crops, as vineyards and orchards. The project is focused on an innovative weed management system, using under row cover crops instead of tillage or herbicides. Cover crops naturally protect the soil, needs fewer interventions and therefore save time and money for farmers. The expected results of the project will focused on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluation of agronomic impacts of under-row cover crops on grapevine or trees - Feasibility of mechanisation of cover crop management (under-row cover crop mowing) - Economic evaluation of the innovative system.
Localisation	Hérault - France
Duration	from 2015 to 2018
Partners	IFVV, Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Hérault, du Gard, des Pyrénées orientales et de l'Aube, Centre Expérimental Horticole, Station d'Expérimentation Régionale pour les Fruits et Légumes
Contact	xavier.delpuech@vignevin.com , +33646320122

4.2 Belgium

4.2.1 Controlled Traffic Farming

Name	Controlled Traffic Farming
Objectives	Benefits of CTF have been proven in research and practice in recent years: controlled traffic lanes prevent soil structure damage and soil compaction in the seedbed between the tracks. This results in optimal growing conditions for soil life and roots and better water storage capacity of soils. CTF also benefits mechanical weed control as fields are earlier accessible and there are no tracks in the seedbed. While these benefits are favourable for organic farming practices, lock-ins make the implementation on farm level not so easy and especially the feasibility for medium sized farms is questioned. This project will support farmers to implement CTF on their specific farm. Three medium sized organic farms (2 with arable crops / vegetables and 1 with mainly grass clover) and one conventional potato grower will be accompanied in the implementation of CTF on their farm. For each case a SWOT-analysis and a CTF-implementation plan will be made. To support this, available knowledge in literature as

	well as existing experiences will be explored together with the concerned farmers. One foreign visit to other CTF-cases is foreseen. The experiences of these 4 cases and current knowledge will be synthesised in a report to inspire other colleagues and will be disseminated by means of a demonstration moment, some networking meetings and publications in written or digital agricultural press. Lock-ins will be proposed to technology firms and research as challenges for further research and development. For this aim one or more round table discussions with stakeholders are planned.
Localisation	Arr. Roeselare - Belgium
Duration	from 2016 to 2017
Partners	Inagro
Contact	info.bio@inagro.be , +32 051 27 32 50

4.2.2 SOCROSense (soil and crop sensing technologies)

Name	SOCROSense (Soil and crop sensing technologies)
Objectives	<p>The aim of SOCROSense is supporting pioneer farmers who have experience with the use of GPS close-sensing techniques to focus on soil and crop sensors. These pioneer farms are a mixed group of farmers, market gardeners, tree nurserymen and agriculture contractors. Together with actors from research institutes and relevant business companies this group wants to create a surplus value and develop a vision for a mid-long term for these sensors. Therefore an analysis shall be made how data of these sensors can be used in a farm and can be exchanged by third parties. Furthermore, an approach on how the data flow of different sensors can be combined and the opportunities that can be reached is investigated.</p> <p>At first an inventory of GPS-sensor technologies will be made up with advantages, disadvantages, potential and technical requirements of commercial or nearly-commercial sensors. Also, the potential of how GPS sensor technology can influence/steer the company crop management will be studied. Moreover, there is a knowledge gap on how data from different sensors can be combined to give an answer on specific questions from pioneer farms. According to the farm type the best combination of GPS-sensors data will be determined. This OG will also carry out a benchmark study in foreign companies which have experience with GPS-sensors. For dissemination, 3 demo activities will be held besides articles in specialised media.</p>
Localisation	Arr. Mechelen - Belgium
Duration	from 2016 to 2018
Partners	Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt, Hooibeekhoeve APB, ILVO, KULeuven, Agrometius bvba, Hillaire van der Haeghe NV, Groentenhof, Boomkwekerij De Bruyn, Denys Carrots, Carolus Trees
Contact	joris.de.nies@proefstation.be , +32 15 30 00 60

4.3 Spain

4.3.1 INNOKUPELA - Technological innovation for the monitoring of the kupelas of Euskal Sagardoa

Name	Technological innovation for the monitoring of the kupelas of Euskal Sagardoa
Localisation	Pais Vasco, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	FUNDACIÓN HAZI FUNDAZIOA
Contact	amontejo@hazi.eus

4.3.2 Pilot system for remote sensing and management of phytosanitary treatments in vineyards

Name	Pilot system for remote sensing and management of phytosanitary treatments in vineyards
Localisation	Cataluña, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	ADV SANT LLORENÇ PENEDÈS SUPERIOR
Contact	adv.vinya@gmail.com

4.3.3 Profitability of the application of new technologies for the achievement of maximum irrigation efficiency in a pilot farm of 100 ha of organic and conventional vineyard

Name	Profitability of the application of new technologies for the achievement of maximum irrigation efficiency in a pilot farm of 100 ha of organic and conventional vineyard.
Localisation	Cataluña, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	CODORNIU SA
Contact	j.esteve@codorniu.es

4.3.4 Control of Monilia spp. In bone fruit: use of prediction models (prophylactic methods)

Name	Control of Monilia spp. In bone fruit: use of prediction models (prophylactic methods)
Localisation	Cataluña, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	ACTEL, SCCL
Contact	cfaro@actel.es

4.3.5 New technologies and strategies of conservation of the apple "Golden Delicious" and varieties of the Gala group

Name	Nuevas tecnologías y estrategias de conservación de la manzana "Golden Delicious" y variedades del grupo Gala
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Localisation	Cataluña, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	FRUCTÍCOLA EMPORDÀ, SL
Contact	mroig@empordasl.com

4.3.6 New methods and technologies to avoid the syndrome of replanting in apple trees

Name	New methods and technologies to avoid the syndrome of replanting in apple trees
Localisation	Cataluña, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	GIRONA FRUITS, SCCL
Contact	jcornell@ironafruits.com

4.3.7 Innovative technologies for combating emerging, re-emerging and transboundary forest pathogens

Name	Innovative technologies for combating emerging, re-emerging and transboundary forest pathogens
Localisation	Galicia, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	Empresa de Transformación Agraria, SA

4.3.8 Application of new technologies towards the reduction of the carbon footprint in intensive horticultural farms in Galicia

Name	Application of new technologies towards the reduction of the carbon footprint in intensive horticultural farms in Galicia
Localisation	Galicia, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	Unión de cooperativas AGACA

4.3.9 Optimization and development of a prototype of bean peeling machine

Name	Optimization and development of a prototype of bean peeling machine
Localisation	Galicia, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	Terras da Mariña, SCG

4.3.10 Design of a tool based on new technologies for the transfer of R&D&I results in the dairy sector

Name	Design of a tool based on new technologies for the transfer of R&D&I results in the dairy sector
Localisation	Galicia, Spain
Duration	from 2015 to 2017
Partners	Asociación Mariñas Betanzos

4.4 Germany

4.4.1 Process development detecting Drains

Name	Process development detecting Drains
Objectives	The BMELV-report regarding the redefinition of less favoured areas (in the European Union) criticizes that there is no resilient data basis concerning the 4 million hectares of drained farmland in Germany. The durability of subsurface drainage pipes that are well maintained amounts to 50 years. The bulk of the drainage systems were already built in the 1970s, hence the durability of the particular pipes has been clearly exceeded in many cases. The failure of drainage systems and hence crop shortfall caused by water logging in the field will increase significantly in the years ahead. The newspaper Schweriner Zeitung speaks of a crisis in the field in the 27 February 2010 issue. To meet the upcoming challenges at the amelioration sector, new innovative approaches for the detection, management and analysis of drainage systems are to be developed und existing approaches are to be crucially improved and optimized in cooperation with partners in agriculture and research.
Localisation	Thüringer - Germany
Duration	started in 2017
Partners	Farmers
Contact	info@agrar-weissensee.de , 036374/2650

4.4.2 Precision liming in Brandenburg

Name	Precision liming in Brandenburg
Objectives	<p>In Brandenburg the majority of agricultural crop land is characterized by reduced yields and soil degradation due to non-satisfying soil pH values. The reasons are manifold for this situation. For example, the soil within a field has a high variability of pH values. As a result, the liming management of agricultural soils in Brandenburg has to be improved and specified. The project includes four different goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The relevance of the soil pH has to be pointed out to farmers - Soil type, humus content and pH value are the most important parameters for precision farming. These parameters shall be determined in a cost-efficient way and on a small scale with the aid of a sensor-based system which has to be developed - In addition a user-friendly decision support system has to be developed, in order to evaluate mapping data and to derive fertilising recommendations in consideration of the circumstances in Brandenburg. Finally the software shall provide more precise application maps - Process engineering solutions for the applications of lime will be developed and imparted by training courses.

Localisation	Brandenburg und Berlin - Germany
Duration	started in 2017
Partners	Farmers
Contact	ekramer@hnee.de , 03334 657 329

4.4.3 Adapting technology in professional fruit growing in the “Alte Land” region

Name	Adapting technology in professional fruit growing in the “Alte Land” region
Objectives	With respect to the regulation for the Altes Land - special area released on 11.03.2015, the aim of the innovation project is to significantly contribute to the further development of the competitiveness and sustainability of the fruit growing sector in lower Saxony. It will contribute to improving the positive impact for the preservation of (natural) resources of the plant protection management strategies used by both integrated and organic fruit farmers.
Localisation	Lower Saxony and Bremen - Germany
Duration	started in 2016
Partners	Farmers
Contact	karsten.klopp@lwk-niedersachsen.de , 04162/60610

4.4.4 Sensor supported irrigation control of potatoes

Name	Sensor supported irrigation control of potatoes
Objectives	The innovation project pursues a new approach to determine the actual drought stress and irrigation demand on the plant directly by measuring the stock's temperature. Plant populations that are provided with sufficient water show an evapotranspiration of more than 8 mm per day. The evaporation cools down the stocks, so that the temperature on the plant's surface is few degrees cooler than the ambient temperature. Insufficient water supply causes stress, which reduces the transpiration of the plant and generates a higher stock's temperature. This temperature can rise up to 3 degrees above the ambient temperature. Within the scope of the project the temperature differences will be recorded contactless and extensively by using an infrared thermographic in order to optimize the irrigation management of the plants. The operational group accompanies the innovation project and attends the implementation in actual agricultural practice.
Localisation	Lower Saxony and Bremen - Germany
Duration	started in 2016
Partners	Farmers
Contact	k.roettcher@ostfalia.de , 0582/698861230

4.4.5 Implementation and further development of an online decision-support-system for an efficient irrigation scheduling of open field vegetable production

Name	Implementation and further development of an online decision-support-system for an efficient irrigation scheduling of open field vegetable production
Objectives	The Geisenheimer Irrigation Scheduling (GS) system for vegetable crops is to be transferred into a practice-oriented decision support system (DSS) in order to enable an efficient sustainable and ecologically sound irrigation scheduling for open-field vegetable production. The tool intends to support vegetable farms in making easy and objective decisions concerning an economical and resource-efficient irrigation. The project aims to strengthen the competitiveness of German vegetable producers in the biggest open-field vegetable production region (Hessia Reed / Vorderpflaz). The compliance with the EU Water Directives, EU Nitrates Directive and the German fertiliser ordinance is meant to be facilitated with the DSS. Furthermore, it aims to provide a big contribution to a sustainable and resource-efficient open field vegetable production. The operational group (OG) plans to test and further develop the prototype GS-Mobile which is a digital assistance management system. The smartphone-compatible application offers the opportunity to control the actual water status from any internet-enabled terminal and to get irrigation recommendations in time.
Localisation	Lower Saxony and Bremen - Germany
Duration	started in 2016
Partners	Farmers
Contact	Jana.Zinkernagel@hs-gm.de , 06722-502511

4.4.6 High-quality technology and organic farming - an innovative approach to control the pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* in potato production

Name	High-quality technology and organic farming - an innovative approach to control the pathogen <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> in potato production
Objectives	The root disease caused by the fungus <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> is a fundamental problem in the production of plant material for potato growing as for a successful cultivation healthy plant material is of very high importance. A direct control of the disease is not possible, but only the interaction between plant production and a preventive integrated pest management is promising. Based on previous research of the University of Kassel, science and industry have co-developed an innovative procedure. It ensures a high protection level of mother and daughter potato tubers through the combination of a simultaneous compost application and potato planting. Compost owns so-called suppressive effects able to control the pathogen. The objective of this project is to establish the procedure to control the <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> and ensure the functionality of the procedural steps. Sub-goals are the compost production at model and practice level, monitoring of impacts by field and demonstration trials, optimisation of the logistics chain and application technology and demonstration of the overall procedure.
Localisation	Hesse - Germany
Duration	started in 2016
Partners	Farmers
Contact	ch.bruns@uni-kassel.de , 05542-981543

4.4.7 Development, test, and implementation of a precision farming system to protect valuable objects below cultivated land

Name	Development, test, and implementation of a precision farming system to protect valuable objects below cultivated land
Objectives	In some areas we find objects of value below cultivated land (like archaeological monuments). To protect these objects cultivation has to be restricted. Aim of the project is to develop, test and implement a precision farming system or technique that automatically and precisely regulates the cultivation depth (or even stops cultivation if necessary) so that valuable objects below the surface are saved from destruction. In addition, the operational group will test the usability of the developed system for fertilization and plant protection purposes. To locate valuable objects in the field GIS data or Shapefiles will be used. A close collaboration between advisers and farmers and a series of field trials are necessary to obtain a usable and reliable system.
Localisation	Saxony - Germany
Duration	started in 2015
Partners	Farmers
Contact	Andreas.Schmidt@exagt.de , 0173-3528960

4.4.8 Optimizing plant protection measures using agricultural meteorology

Name	Optimizing plant protection measures using agricultural meteorology
Objectives	By using information on weather forecasts farmers could improve the efficiency of their plant protection measures. The project aims at providing the data base for a tool or model that could predict the effectiveness of growth regulators and plant protection products depending on the meteorological conditions at the time of application. To obtain reliable results the operational group will conduct three years of exact field trials. This model, which requires besides plant protection product specifications only meteorological prognosis as variable input data, could be integrated into ISIP or made available to farmers as a new advisory tool.
Localisation	Saxony - Germany
Duration	started in 2015
Partners	Farmers
Contact	Peter.Albrecht.Nossen@t-online.de , 035242-64464

4.4.9 Optimized pasture management - smart grazing

Name	Optimized pasture management - smart grazing
Objectives	The feeding basis of milk production has dramatically changed in Schleswig Holstein and nationwide in the last decades. The grazing of dairy cattle has been increasingly replaced by intensive livestock housing with feeding of grass and maize silage and concentrated feed. As a consequence there lacks a well-founded and scientifically sound data basis for assessing pasture services in SH. This OG has set itself the goal to close this data gap and to correct existing deficiencies in pasture expertise in the country. The overall objective of the OG is to gather the performance potential of pasture in terms of yield and quality in the main landscape-types of SH. From this measured data, a model "smart grazing" (a forecasting tool) should be developed that is able to operate in conjunction with the predictions of the German

	Meteorological Service to provide real-time data on current growth rates and feed quality parameters on a high technical level (mobile app) and, together with pilot-farms, identify landscape type-specific problems of grazing and provide solutions for these.
Localisation	Schleswig-Holstein - Germany
Duration	started in 2015
Partners	Farmers
Contact	ftaube@gfo.uni-kiel.de , 0431-8802134

4.5 Greece

In Greece, there are no officially operating Operational Groups, but the first call for such Groups to be formed will be opened on June 2017.

5 Relevant platforms on SFT

5.1 European level

5.1.1 TP ORGANICS - European Technology Platform

Name	TP ORGANICS - European Technology Platform
Website address	www.tporganics.eu
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>TP Organics is one of the 40 European Technology Platforms (ETP) officially recognized by the European Commission. Its main OBJECTIVE is to leverage the organic sector's contribution to sustainable farming and food production.</p> <p>To achieve this OBJECTIVE, TP Organics actively engages the whole food supply chain from farmers to consumers. It unites large companies, small & medium enterprises, researchers, farmers, consumers and civil society organizations active in the organic value chain from production, input & supply, to food processing, marketing and consumption.</p> <p>The platform identifies the research needs of the organic sector and agro-ecological or low-input farmers and then relays research priorities to the policy-makers. TP Organics also informs its members about funding opportunities for research & innovation and promotes knowledge exchange between farmers, companies and researchers.</p>
Partners	http://tporganics.eu/national-platform-members/
Contact	http://tporganics.eu/about-us/ and +32 (0) 2 416 27 61

5.1.2 PLANTS FOR THE FUTURE – European Technology Platform

Name	PLANTS FOR THE FUTURE – European Technology Platform
Website address	http://www.plantetp.org/
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>The European Technology Platform (ETP) 'Plants for the Future' is a stakeholder forum for the plant sector with members from industry, academia and the farming community. It serves as a platform for all stakeholders concerned with plants to provide their views and represent their interests in an open discussion process. It provides a 20-year vision, a short-, medium- and long-term Strategic Research Agenda for Europe's plant sector and sets up strategic action plans to promote Innovation, Research and Education in the plant sector.</p> <p>Developing plant for the future requires an integrated action including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RESEARCH (generation of knowledge about plants, their production and their valorisation into products) - INNOVATION (transformation of knowledge into practice and products) - EDUCATION (development of skilful and knowledgeable people for research, industry and the farming community)
Partners	http://www.plantetp.org/about/members
Contact	secretariat@plantetp.eu

5.1.3 EU ROBOTICS – European Technology Platform

Name	EU ROBOTICS – European Technology Platform
Website address	https://www.eu-robotics.net/eurobotics
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>EU Robotics AISBL (Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif) is a Brussels based international non-profit association for all stakeholders in European robotics. EU Robotics builds upon the success of the European Robotics Technology Platform (EUROP) and the academic network of EURON, and will not only continue the cooperation but will also strengthen the bond between members of these two community driven organisations. This ETP is leading towards the establishment of only one sustainable organisation for the European robotics community as a whole.</p> <p>One of the association's main missions is to collaborate with the European Commission to develop and implement a strategy and a roadmap for research, technological development and innovation in robotics, in view of the launch of the next framework program Horizon 2020. Towards this end, EU Robotics was formed to engage from the private side in a contractual Public-Private Partnership, SPARC, with the European Union as the public side.</p> <p>The objectives of EU Robotics are to boost European robotics research, development and innovation and to foster a positive perception of robotics. It aims at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - strengthening competitiveness and ensuring industrial leadership of manufacturers, providers and end users of robotics technology-based systems and services; - the widest and best uptake of robotics technologies and services for professional and private use; - the excellence of the science base of European robotics.
Partners	https://www.eu-robotics.net/eurobotics/membership/list-of-members/index.html
Contact	secretariat@eu-robotics.net

5.1.4 ROBOHUB

Name	ROBOHUB
Website address	http://robohub.org/
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>Robohub is a non-profit online communication platform that brings together experts in robotics research, start-ups, business, and education from across the globe. Robohub mission is to connect the robotics community to the rest of the world. Content-area specialists curate all incoming articles to make sure that reporting is truthful, fair and balanced, and in-house editors ensure that all content meets the highest editorial standards for language and clarity. Embedded comments and an active presence on Google+, Facebook and Twitter further help to promote discussion and debate.</p> <p>Robohub's genetic code:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A belief that knowledge should be open and shared - A belief that anyone can educate themselves and make informed decisions if they have

	<p>straightforward access to clear, relevant information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A belief that experts are ideally positioned to communicate directly with the public - A deep sense of responsibility to the scientific community
Contact	info@robohub.org / +41 22 548 13 12

5.1.5 E-AGRICULTURE

Name	E-AGRICULTURE
Website address	http://www.e-agriculture.org/
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>e-Agriculture is a global Community of Practice, where people from all over the world exchange information, ideas, and resources related to the use ICT for sustainable agriculture and rural development.</p> <p>With over 14,000 members from 170 countries and territories, the e-Agriculture Community is made up of individual stakeholders such as information and communication specialists, researchers, farmers, students, policy makers, business people, development practitioners, and others.</p> <p>The members have a common interest that brings us together: improving policies and processes around the use of ICT in support of agriculture and rural development, in order to have a positive impact on rural livelihoods.</p>
Contact	http://www.e-agriculture.org/content/contact-us

5.2 National Level

5.2.1 Spain

Spanish Technology Platform on sustainable agriculture

Name	Spanish Technology Platform on sustainable agriculture
Website address	www.agriculturasostenible.org
Type of initiative	Platform
timeframe	
Objectives	<p>Analysis of the environment of the different sectors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the key processes where the greatest consumption of resources, destined to the production of agro-livestock raw materials, is carried out, in order to identify opportunities for improvement in the efficiency of the use of resources. - Evaluate national and international technologies as benchmarks for competitiveness. - Prioritize the areas of action by sector. <p>Establishment of sector and multisector strategies.</p>

	<p>Focusing on the improvement of sustainability indices at the sector level and at the global level of the value chain.</p> <p>Recommendation of actions to be carried out from different perspectives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technologies to put into practice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Generation of new technologies ✓ Adaptation of technologies already developed and tested - Redesign of processes - Intersectoral cooperation: Creation of an integrated technological network <p>Institutional advice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administrations and Public Entities to make use of the knowledge derived from the implementation of the Platform. - Private Entities from the individual company to the sectoral groupings within the corresponding associations, to improve their competitiveness in a sustainable production environment
Contact	administracion@agriculturasostenible.org

The Spanish wine technology platform

Name	The Spanish wine technology platform
Website address	www.ptvino.com
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>This is a forum for the different agents in the Spanish wine industry to come together and deliberate, with the aim of becoming a true business-science network of cooperation capable of defining a common Strategy in the field of R&D&I, led by business.</p> <p>The Wine Technology Platform is aimed at all those involved in the area of research, technological development and innovation of Spain's wine industry, integrating:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The whole value chain: including wineries, auxiliary industries, nurseries, etc. - All stakeholders: including companies, business associations, regulatory boards, universities, public and private research centres, technology centres, oenological research stations, related technology platforms, public and private institutions, etc. - The whole area of Spain: all autonomous regions - With the aim of INTERNATIONALISING the sector
Contact	http://www.ptvino.com/index.php/en/contact.html

Spanish Platform on water and irrigation

Name	Spanish Platform on water and irrigation
Website address	www.plataformaagua.org
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>The Spanish Water Technology Platform is a R&D&I network in the water sector whose main objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate added value for Partners, Sector and Society - To promote participation and collaboration in R&D&I between national and international entities, public and private, strengthening the collaboration between the scientific community and the business sector - Design and implement a Strategic Research Agenda - Identify and promote R&D&I projects - Encourage technology transfer - Promote the formation of the productive network and users <p>The Platform promotes sectoral R&D&I, and the Spanish participation in the international panorama, and especially of Spanish public companies and centres in programs, initiatives and projects of the European Union.</p>
Contact	http://www.plataformaagua.org/index.php/contacto

5.2.2 France

API AGRO – Data and services platform for agriculture ecosystem

Name	API AGRO – Data and services platform for agriculture ecosystem
Website address	http://www.api-agro.fr
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	<p>The main aim of the platform is, via new channels of dissemination by the web, to make a catalogue of data available as well as calculation functions produced by the institutes' researchers and engineers. This approach is comparable to those of the major economic players who strive to strengthen their presence on the web by developing more and more APIs. But the originality of the institutes' project lies in associating several partners who provide data around a single platform thus covering the needs of the entire vegetable and animal farming industry.</p>
Contact	support@api-agro.fr

5.2.3 Netherlands

Praktijkcentrum precisielandbouw

Name	Praktijkcentrum precisielandbouw
Website address	https://www.smartindustry.nl/fieldlabs/praktijkcentrum-voor-precisielandbouw/
Type of initiative	Platform
Objectives	Create access to data for precision agriculture for (collective) use by agricultural companies, suppliers, industrie en knowledge institutes. The centre offers demonstration and test facilities on location.
Contact	peter.paree@zlto.nl

6 Relevant accelerators on SFT

6.1 FRACTALS

Name	Fractals
Website address	http://fractals-fp7.com/
Type of initiative	Fiware Accelerator
timeframe	-
Objectives	<p>FRACTALS aims to support the community of innovative ICT SMEs and web-entrepreneurs to develop FIWARE based applications with high market potential, addressing the needs of the agricultural sector. FRACTALS Call was open to all European SMEs and web-entrepreneurs but additionally focused on areas which are considered as "white spots" (Balkans, South East Europe).</p> <p>FRACTALS offered between 50,000 and 150,000 €, reaching a total amount of 5.5 million euros, to 50-60 SMEs and web-entrepreneurs to develop applications based on FIWARE technologies for the Agricultural Sector. The Open Call to SMEs was published on November 30th, 2014 and was open until February 28th, 2015.</p>
Partners	http://fractals-fp7.com/index.php/about/consortium
Contact	gchatzikostas@gmail.com

6.2 H2020 KATANA

Name	Katana – Cutting edge tech in agribusiness
Website address	http://katanaproject.eu/
Type of initiative	Accelerator
Objectives	<p>The EU-funded business accelerator KATANA will support the development of innovative, tech-based products and services in the agrifood sector, by providing the best 100 applicants with 2,000 euros funding, while the best 10 teams in terms of market attractiveness and performance will be granted 100,000 euros each. As an additional service, KATANA provides support in the form of three free-of-charge technology platforms.</p> <p>KATANA is open for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entrepreneurs who want to get their own business started - Start-ups that want to get investor ready

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SMEs that want to experiment with new products - Researchers who want to explore how to commercialize a technology
Contact	Dr. Mladen Radisic - dissemination manager; mladen.voict@gmail.com

6.3 SMARTAGRIFOOD

Name	Smart Food and Agribusiness - Future Internet for Safe and Healthy Food from Farm to Fork
Website address	http://www.smartagrifood.eu
Type of initiative	Accelerator
Objectives	<p>SMARTAGRIFOOD:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aims to boost the application and use of future internet ICTs in the Agri-Food domain - Increases the competitiveness of the European Agri-Food domain - Affects a huge number of SMEs in the Agri-Food domain throughout Europe
Contact	http://www.smartagrifood.eu/contact

6.4 ORIZONT

orizont

Name	Smart Food and Agribusiness - Future Internet for Safe and Healthy Food from Farm to Fork.
Website address	http://www.orizont.es/en/
Type of initiative	Accelerator
Objectives	<p>Agri-food (including smart farming) acceleration programme of Navarre region</p> <p>OBJECTIVE: accelerate early stage companies within the agrifood sector through an acceleration programme that includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 110.000€ of financial support - 6 months of acceleration, including support for business model, business plan development and making of contact sales as well as mentoring and coaching for personal skills and company development, - Access to facilities, such as shared working space, pilot floor for R&D and pre-test with Kitchen and Laboratory, networking space as well as industrial units adapted to the requirements of the agrifood sector (www.ciudadagroalimentaria.es).
Contact	http://www.orizont.es/en/apply/

7 Relevant events on SFT

7.1 International events

7.1.1 AGRITECHNICA

Name	AgriTechnica
Website address	https://www.agritechnica.com/en/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	Every 2 years (from 12th to 18th November 2017)
Place	Hanover - Germany
Description	<p>Innovations in agricultural machinery and equipment and the latest solutions and concepts for the future of plant production are presented every two years at AGRITECHNICA in Hanover, Germany. The world's leading exhibition for agricultural machinery and equipment will be held again from 12 to 18 November 2017.</p> <p>More than 2,900 exhibitors from 52 countries are presenting ag machinery for professional plant production. On seven days 452,000 expert visitors from 115 countries came to the fair, including 98,000 international visitors.</p> <p>With its top-flight technical programme featuring a large number of international events such as congresses, workshops and forums, AGRITECHNICA is considered to be the most important forum for the future of the agricultural sector.</p> <p>This is the venue where technology trends are identified and displayed and where all key questions concerning the future of agriculture and agricultural machinery and equipment are addressed.</p> <p>The international event series "Ag Machinery International - Access to emerging markets" was held once again in 2015 too. The different days of the trade fair were devoted to different national agricultural machinery markets – exploring market potentials, market access, financing frameworks and technology requirements. After each event there was an opportunity to take part in a contact forum targeting initiation of international business relations.</p> <p>For the first time this year there was an event revolving around component markets with a focus on the BRIC countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China).</p>
Target public	Farmers, dealers, researchers, machinery industries
Contact details	https://www.agritechnica.com/en/exhibitorservice/contact/

7.1.2 SIMA – Paris International Business Show

Name	SIMA – Salon International du Machinisme Agricole
Website address	https://en.simaonline.com/

Type of event.	Fair
Date	Every 2 years (from February 26 th to March 2 nd 2017)
Place	Paris Nord Villepinte, France
Description	<p>Since its creation in 1922, SIMA has continued to grow, becoming the essential event for agriculture all over the world. Thanks to its international network, SIMA disseminates all the solutions dedicated to the development of agriculture across the planet.</p> <p>SIMA 2017 will take place from 26 February to 2 March 2017 in Paris Nord Villepinte, France.</p> <p>SIMA key figures from SIMA 2015:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1,770 companies from 42 countries - 13 exhibition sectors - 238,848 entries from 142 countries - 300 international delegations <p>13 business sectors are represented in the SIMA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traction, soil tillage, harvesting equipment, services - Pro equipment for green spaces - Irrigation - Rural and forest area, wood energy - Services and institutions - Plant protection - Equipment for tropical and special crops - Crops, harvesting, storage, packaging of beets, potato, fruit & vegetable - Handling, transport - Biogas - Milking and breeding equipment - Storage buildings - Spare parts and components, precision farming, services\
Target public	Farmers, dealers, researchers, machinery industries
Contact details	https://en.simaonline.com/SIMA/About-SIMA

7.1.3 FIMA - International Fair of Agricultural Machinery

Name	FIMA - International Fair of Agricultural Machinery
Website address	https://www.feriazaragoza.es/fima-agricola-2018
Type of event.	Fair
Date	from 20 to 24 of February 2018
Place	Zaragoza, Spain
Description	<p>FIMA is the major showcase for the agricultural world in Southern Europe.</p> <p>The mechanization and the technological innovations will show to the professionals the best way to make more profitable their exploitations, hence improving both performance and yields. The prominent role of the farmer will highlight in an event that focuses particularly on the Agriculture of the Mediterranean area and permanently arises the situation of the European and worldwide agriculture.</p>
Target public	Farmers, dealers, researchers, machinery industries

Contact details	https://www.feriazaragoza.es/fima-agricola-2018/comunicacion/contacto ; + 34 976 76 47 00
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7.1.4 FIMART

Name	FIMART
Website address	www.fimart.es
Type of event.	Fair
Date	from 20 to 22 of October 2017
Place	Córdoba, España
Description	<p>FIMART Innovation Fair Smart Rural presents technological solutions applicable to the rural world in general and, specifically, to companies in the agrifood value chain in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advanced software - Precision farming - Sensoring - Internet of things - Bigdata and its application to business intelligence - Artificial intelligence - Unmanned flights - Robotization - Energy efficiency <p>FIMART aims to create an environment of international reference in rural and agrifood innovation, combining public and private interests, that is sustainable in the medium and long term, in a large collective project that contributes to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation in companies of the agrifood value chain, improving their overall competitive position and the international trade balance of the sectors concerned. - The attraction of talent and investment in innovation and technology to be applied to the rural world in general and to the agrifood value chain sectors in particular - The generation of quality jobs and income in the sectors concerned
Target public	
Contact details	feria@fimart.es ; (+34) 957 656 852

7.1.5 VINITECH-SIFEL

Name	VINITECH - Sifel
Website address	http://www.vinitech-sifel.com/
Type of event.	Trade show
Date	from 27 th to 29 th of November 2018
Place	Parc des expositions in Bordeaux (France)
Description	This exhibition brings together 4 sectors (Vineyards and Orchards, Wine Production,

	<p>Bottling and Packaging, Services and Training) spread over 65,000 m² with multiples areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A vibrant ideas Forum for exchanging information and networking - A New Products & Innovations area to showcase technological wine equipment - An international business convention <p>During 3 days, this event which take place in Bordeaux every two years gathers more than 850 exhibitors and around 50 000 visitors.</p>
Target public	
Contact details	Aurélie Sébastian - a.sebastian@bordeaux-expo.com

7.1.6 EFITA 2017

Name	EFITA 2017
Website address	http://www.efita2017.org/
Type of event.	Conference
Date	from 2 nd to 6 th of July, 2017
Place	Montpellier - France
Description	<p>11th Conference on Information Technology in Agriculture, Food and the Environment. EFITA is the European conference dedicated to the future use of ICT in the agri-food sector, bioresource and biomass sector. It was launched and is supported by the European Federation for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food and the Environment (EFITA). The first EFITA was held in 1997, and 2017 is the 11th of the series. Montpellier, France, is most happy to welcome the event. It will take place in the pleasant site of the renowned Montpellier SupAgro school. A nice atmosphere for knowledge sharing and thinking the future of ICT technologies within the agri-food and bioresource sectors will be provided.</p>
Target public	-
Contact details	Jean-Pierre Chanet – IRSTEA : jean-pierre.chanet@irstea.fr

7.1.7 GFIAEurope17 - Global Forum for Innovations in Agriculture Europe

Name	GFIAEurope17 - Global Forum for Innovations in Agriculture Europe
Website address	http://gfiaeurope.com/
Type of event.	Forum
Date	Annual event (from 9 to 10 May 2017)
Place	Jaabeurs Expo Centre, Utrecht, the Netherlands.
Description	<p>The world's largest dedicated expo of sustainable agriculture solutions. When GFIA was launched in 2014 at the invitation of the Abu Dhabi government, it leveraged partnerships with 40 powerful organisations including the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the UN, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, and the World Bank, that wanted a platform to show the world how technology gives us the only real chance of feeding nine billion people without destroying the environment. Now an internationally acclaimed annual event in Abu Dhabi, GFIA is the world's largest showcase of sustainable agriculture innovations. It is not only a forum for stakeholders to discuss policy, strategy and solutions for a food secure future, but hosts a large exhibition where suppliers can meet thousands of farmers and procurement managers right along</p>

	the value chain. The GFIA team that delivered the largest agriculture event in the Middle East in 2016 will be bringing GFIA Europe to the Netherlands for the first time.
Target public	-
Contact details	info@InnovationsInAgriculture.com ; http://gfiaeurope.com/en-GB/About/Contact-us

7.1.8 ISAPEP'17

Name	ISAPEP'17
Website address	http://ke.cau.ac.kr/intenv2017/index.html
Type of event.	Workshop
Date	21 st and 22 nd of August, 2017
Place	Seoul, South Korea
Description	<p>The 1st International Workshop on Intelligent Systems for Agriculture Production and Environment Protection</p> <p>This workshop will focus on the use of intelligent systems to overcome the issues related to the lack of productivity of farming systems and environmental degradation. This will involve the integration of solutions from different disciplines such as engineering, telecommunications, mathematics/statistics and agricultural, environmental and computer science. The workshop will represent an opportunity to debate the state-of-the-art, cutting-edge challenges and the collaborations required.</p> <p>Areas of interest include, but are not limited to, the following ones:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agriculture Information Technologies - Smart farming - Precision agriculture - Environmental degradation assessment and rehabilitation - Environmental monitoring - Linking environmental characterisation and broad management - Intelligent forecasting applications - Intelligent applications for ecological disaster management - Intelligent waste management - Sensor development - Multi sensor and data fusion
Target public	-
Contact details	info@InnovationsInAgriculture.com ; http://gfiaeurope.com/en-GB/About/Contact-us

7.1.9 EIP-AGRI seminar 'Digital Innovation Hubs: mainstreaming digital agriculture'

Name	EIP-AGRI seminar 'Digital Innovation Hubs: mainstreaming digital agriculture'
Website address	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-seminar-digital-innovation-hubs-mainstreaming-digital-agriculture
Type of event.	Seminar
Date	1 st and 2 nd June 2017
Place	Kilkenny, Ireland
Description	The EU is supporting the development of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). A DIH is a support facility that helps both, agriculture businesses and ICT companies - within their region or beyond - to become more competitive by improving their business/production processes as well as products and services by means of digital technology. DIHs act as

	<p>one-stop-shop enabling any business to access the latest knowledge, expertise and technology for testing and experimenting with digital innovations. They provide connections with investors, facilitate access to financing for digital transformations, and help connect users in agriculture and ICT suppliers of digital innovations across the value chain.</p> <p>The main objective of this event is to enable policy makers, research and technology organisations, the agriculture sector and investors to share knowledge, expertise and needs to develop Digital Innovation Hubs for agriculture.</p>
Target public	-
Contact details	+32 2 543 73 48 servicepoint@eip-agri.eu

7.1.10 Land.Technik AgEng 2017

Name	Land.Technik AgEng 2017
Website address	https://www.vdi-wissensforum.de/en/event/internationale-landtechnik/?utm_source=CfP&utm_campaign=12TA001017&utm_medium=email&utm_content=17C12EM1
Type of event.	Conference
Date	10-11 November 2017
Place	Hannover Germany
Description	<p>With over 1,000 participants in 2015, the International Conference on Agricultural Engineering Land.Technik AgEng is the most important event for the international community of agricultural engineers. The event provides the ideal mix of technically in-depth lectures and networking opportunities. Innovations in the areas of tractors, powertrains and harvesting technology as well as automation in agricultural machinery and the Precision Farming method are at the centre of the conference in 2017. The conference is the kick-off for the AGRITECHNICA, the world's most important exhibition for agricultural machinery. Submission of Abstracts by 31 March 2017.</p>
Target public	Agricultural engineers from research and manufacturers
Contact details	In case of queries: +49(0)2116214-201 email: wissensforum@vdi.de

7.1.11 Field Robot Event - FRE 2017

Name	Field Robot Event
Website address	http://www.fieldrobot.com/event/
Type of event.	Student competition / education event
Date	Summer 2017
Place	Harper Adams Univeristy, UK
Description	<p>Designing, constructing and most important of all: testing. This is what happens at the Field Robot Event where students leave their lecture rooms and go out into the fields. Students compete in an international competition and put their self-constructed autonomous robots to the test. The Field Robot Event was established by the University Wageningen, the Netherlands but moves around Europe and international teams show up to compete with the best.</p> <p>The CLAAS Foundation supports the organization of the event and also individual teams.</p>
Target public	Students: agricultural engineering, robotics, ICT and related disciplines
Contact details	http://www.harper-adams.ac.uk/staff/profile.cfm?id=201030

7.1.12 International VDI Conference - Smart Farming

Name	Internation VDI Conference - Smart Farming
Website address	https://www.vdi-wissensforum.de/en/event/smart-farming/
Type of event.	Conference
Date	9-10 May 2017
Place	Dusseldorf, Germany
Description	<p>Providing farmers with the right technology allows them to optimize (moreover: minimize!) their use of pesticides and the like while maintaining a high output with reasonable investments.</p> <p>Learn about the latest developments in the field of “Smart Farming”. The international VDI conference “Smart Farming” will provide the opportunity to meet with experts and discuss the hot topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Situational Awareness” for farmers and engineers in the field - Integrated sensor technology in farming equipment - How the IoT affects agricultural operations - Data acquisition and handling for real-time process adjustments - Application of smart devices - using IT to drive processes - Farming management with tailored software solutions - Using Drones in Smart Farming - Innovations for future farming technologies
Target public	Farmers, cooperatives, equipment suppliers, robotic manufacturers, chemical industry, public administration, researchers, advisors
Contact details	wissensforum@vdi.de

7.2 National Level

7.2.1 Spain

SMAGUA

Name	SMAGUA
Website address	http://www.demoagro.es/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	From 7 to 9 March 2017
Place	Feria de Zaragoza, Spain
Description	Feria de Zaragoza provides the professionals all the relevant tools to improve the present and the future of the hydrological sector with the celebration of SMAGUA 2017. The International Water and Irrigation Exhibition offers innovation, opportunities and professionalism, during an exhibition consolidated and guaranteed for the market.
Target public	
Contact details	http://www.feriazaragoza.com/smagua-2017/communication/contact

FAME INNOWA

Name	FAME INNOWA
Website address	http://fameinnowa.es/en/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	From 29 th March to 1 st April 2017
Place	Murica, Spain
Description	<p>In 2017, INNOWA, International Forum of Knowledge and Agricultural Innovation, will be celebrated again which complements the trade exhibition. It is a certainly valuable addition and an opportunity to further develop solutions in a sector enjoying constant evolution.</p> <p>Through technical seminars, conferences, you will be able to know the results of the technology that is being developed and implement currently in the Region of Murcia. INNOWA is as an environment to promote research, innovation technology transfer and practical knowledge, through close collaboration between universities.</p>
Target public	
Contact details	T. 968 33 63 83 ; F. 968 57 83 18 / 62 ; ifepa@ifepa.es

DEMOAGRO

Name	DEMOAGRO
Website address	http://www.demoagro.es/
Type of event.	Field showcase
Date	9,10,11 May 2017
Place	La Granja de San Clemente, Cuenca
Description	Event that showcases the latest technological innovations in agricultural machinery on field.
Target public	
Contact details	demoagro@demoagro.es ; +34 91 411 33 68

FENAVIN – Wine National Fair

Name	FENAVIN – Wine National Fair
Website address	http://www.fenavin.com/home.php
Type of event.	Fair
Date	9,10,11 May 2017
Place	Ciudad real, Spain
Description	<p>FENAVIN is the Spanish wine industry's most important global trade fair. This is how both the EL PAÍS newspaper, in an article in its Business supplement, and ICEX, refer to the National Wine Fair</p> <p>It is an opinion shared by Spanish wineries and cooperatives, which have supported FENAVIN as a tool for boosting the Spanish wine sector at home and abroad since it first opened its doors. The sector appreciates the efficient system used by the Fair year after year. The Fair's management continues to work towards the same goal: Helping demand and supply to meet and do business using sensible and efficient business tools.</p> <p>This system, focused on the needs of buyers, has turned FENAVIN, in just eight years, into Spain's most important wine industry trade fair and the only one offering a focused business environment. This is why, at FENAVIN 2015, 1,361 vine growers, from all over Spain, attended the event, held in seven pavilions. Almost all the Spanish Designation of Origin regions signed trade agreements at Spain's top wine event.</p>

Target public	
Contact details	fenavincontact@fenavin.com ; +34 926 295 628

INFOAGRO exhibition

Name	INFOAGRO exhibition
Website address	http://www.infoagroexhibition.com/en/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	10, 11, 12 May 2017
Place	Almeria, Spain
Description	The business epicenter for agricultural producers This fair is designed in order for the farmer to be the protagonist of the event and to be in touch with everything needed to increase their farm production. The organization of the fair knows that for both companies and farmers, time is gold. It is for this reason that meeting rooms are created. The main objective of this initiative is to let the companies, who set up their stand, receive visitors in an intimate way.
Target public	Farmers, companies
Contact details	exhibition@infoagro.com ; Phone: 0034 902 300103

Spanish Congress on irrigation

Name	Spanish Congress on irrigation
Website address	http://www.congresoriegos-aeryd.org
Type of event.	Congress
Date	from 6 to 8 of June 2017
Place	Tarragona, España
Description	The XXXV National Irrigation Congress is organized by the Spanish Association of Irrigation and Drainage (AERYD), with the support of the General Community of Irrigation of the Canal de la Ebro (CGRCADE). This Congress is held every year and is open to the participation of all people interested in irrigation, having the possibility of finding a space for the meeting, presentation, debate and discussion of ideas, methods, news, and experiences, that contribute to the scientific and technological advance in the different thematic areas of irrigation. In this edition of the Congress a special invitation is made to farmers, consultants, designers and engineers to present their technical applications to the end user, to face the new challenges and demands of innovation, modernization and sustainability in the irrigation of the 21st century .
Target public	
Contact details	aeryd@aeryd.es ; (+34) 915332253

Congress of the tele-detection Spanish organization

Name	Congress of the tele-detection Spanish organization
Website address	https://www.aet2017.es
Type of event.	Congress
Date	from 3 to 7 of October 2017
Place	Zaragoza, Spain
Description	The next congress, the XVII AET will take place in Murcia in October 2017 under the motto "New platforms and sensors of remote sensing" applied to water management,

	<p>Agriculture and the Environment, among other issues.</p> <p>The objective of this edition will be to promote a meeting between the academic community and the business sector that develops new platforms, the scientific environment of remote sensing and those responsible for water, agriculture and environmental management at different scales.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Field scale using mobile sensors installed on agricultural platforms - Airborne scale, with sensors installed on new low cost platforms such as drones - Satellite scale. Where aspects related to multi / hyperspectral and thermal image analysis, SAR or LiDAR data will be addressed.
Target public	
Contact details	congreso@aet2017.es ; +34 968366751

Fruit Attraction

Name	Congress of the tele-detection Spanish organization
Website address	http://www.ifema.es/fruitattraction_06/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	From 18 th to 20 th of October 2017
Place	
Description	<p>More than 1,500 companies from the entire fruit and vegetable sector value chain are expected to take part, representing a 20% increase after the success achieved in 2016. One factor that has made this one of the sector's main international events is the fact that it takes place in October, a key moment when fruit and vegetable suppliers and buyers sign agreements.</p> <p>Southern Europe is becoming firmly established as an important, expanding hub for the global fruit and vegetable trade, and a gateway to Europe from Latin America. This gives Fruit Attraction strategic importance as a major platform and international meeting point for fresh produce operators.</p> <p>The organisers of this trade show have worked hard to put a strategic roadmap in place that will allow them to continue offering international markets a highly efficient marketing tool in years to come, which is why the 2017 edition will be packed with new features.</p>
Target public	
Contact details	fruitattraction@ifema.es

7.2.2 France

LES CULTURALES

Name	Les culturales
Website address	http://www.lesculturales.com/
Type of event.	Field fair
Date	The 12th Culturales® will take place the 14 th and 15 th of June
Place	Ferme 112, next to Reims
Description	<p>Around Innovations and performance topics, exhibitors will present their results and innovations aiming to improve arable crop production performances.</p> <p>During 2 days you will discover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 20 ha of exhibition - 150 experts

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovations Show, a real arable crop innovation show-case - 200 exhibitors
Target public	
Contact details	x.gautier@arvalisinstitutduvegetal.fr

LES TERRENALES

Name	Les Terrenales
Website address	http://en.lesterrenales.com/
Type of event.	Field fair
Date	previous Terrenales took place May 28 th & 29 th 2015
Place	St-Martin du Fouilloux (49) near Angers
Description	<p>Les Terrenales, initiated by the TERRENA cooperative, aims to bring together Ecologically Intensive Farming innovations (Ecosystem functionality, Knowledge of the living world, Digital and sensors, Energy-Machines-Robots) and increase their visibility, in one location, over two days. This is the leading event for those who choose to experiment with, and are interested in exploring all the options for agriculture of the future. In constant evolution, innovation is enriched by feedback from Forward Looking Farmers. On their farms, these professionals are already using technologies and methods to optimise productivity: using fewer chemicals and fossil fuels and less water. By adding value to their production, they also save time and money.</p> <p>The 2015 event designed with a range of agricultural partners, will highlight the necessity for change to be brought “together” through innovation and identification of the positive triggers for change wherever they may be found, via: farmers, farming professionals and engineers, biologists, researchers, veterinarians, biodiversity specialists, etc.</p> <p>At Les Terrenales, discover real-life innovation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Watch real-time demonstrations and highlights under the covered stands. - Testimonials from forward looking farmers® - Workshops presenting the latest ideas, solutions and innovations offered by Ecologically Intensive Farming (EIF®). - Concrete solutions allowing the pooling of knowledge and experience and the emergence of new ideas. - “Terrenales Challenges” with prizes awarded in each category.
Target public	
Contact details	http://en.lesterrenales.com/contact-3/

SALON AUX CAHMPS

Name	Salon aux champs
Website address	http://www.salonauxchamps.cuma.fr/
Type of event.	Field fair
Date	Every year, in 2017 : the 30th and 31st of August 2017
Place	This year, the event will take place in Lisieux (Normandie)
Description	This event brings together professionals who want to exchange about their agricultural activities and actualities. The Salon aux champs is organized by FRCUMA Ouest and is taken place every 2 years, in a different department in the Grand Ouest region.
Target public	
Contact details	head of the event – Gilles Picard - gilles.picard@cuma.fr

7.2.3 Germany

ZASSO FIELD DAY 2017

Name	ZASSO FIELD DAY 2017
Website address	http://zasso.eu/event-extern/zasso-field-days-2017/
Type of event.	Demonstration day
Date	May 2 nd 2017
Place	Aachen Germany
Description	The first demonstration day of the digital herbicide in Europe A showcase applications for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urban weed control - Consumer- semi-professional weed control - precision Agriculture weed control
Target public	
Contact details	info@zasso.de

7.2.4 United Kingdom

ECPA 2017 – The 11th European Conference on Precision Agriculture

Name	ECPA 2017 – The 11 th European Conference on Precision Agriculture
Website address	https://ecpa.delegate-everything.co.uk
Type of event.	Conference
Date	from 16 th to 20th of July 2017
Place	Edinburgh, United Kingdom
Description	It is 20 years since the first ECPA conference and the UK organisers are pleased to welcome the return of the conference to the UK and to Edinburgh. The conference will continue with a successful format of previous conferences building in strong industry sessions and participation. The theme of 'Innovating through Research' will enable all involved in Precision Agriculture to participate. Oral and poster presentations will be welcomed from authors on any precision agriculture topic though particularly welcome in the list of topics shown in the Programme section. All prospective authors and presenters should view the 'Key Dates' section to ensure they can meet the deadlines. Registration for ECPA 2017 is not yet open, but anyone can record their interest and receive regular updates by pre-registering.
Target public	
Contact details	info@ecpa2017.com

CEREALS 2017

Name	CEREALS 2017
Website address	http://www.cerealsevent.co.uk/
Type of event.	Field fair
Date	14th & 15th June 2017
Place	Boothby Graffoe, Lincolnshire, United Kingdom
Description	Cereals: the technical event for the arable industry
Target public	24000 farmers, agronomists and industry professionals.

Contact details	natalie.reed@haymarket.com ; +44 (0)1788 892039
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PRECISION FARMING EVENT

Name	PRECISION FARMING EVENT
Website address	http://precisionfarmingevent.co.uk/
Type of event.	
Date	Tuesday 18th October 2017
Place	Lincoln Road, Newark-on-Trent, Nottinghamshire, UK
Description	The Precision Farming Event provides a unique opportunity to get hands on with the latest technology, but also discusses new ideas with industry-leading experts and gives you the chance to make the most of your existing systems and data.
Target public	farmers, agronomists and industry professionals.
Contact details	admin@farm-smart.co.uk , http://precisionfarmingevent.co.uk/contact/ ; +44 08454900142

CROPTec

Name	Croptec
Website address	http://www.croptecshow.com/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	November 29 th and 30 th 2017
Place	East of England Showground, Peterborough
Description	<p>CropTec, the essential technical and business event for arable and mixed farmers, their advisers and associated industries, will be packed with innovative features and content. To encourage knowledge exchange between the farming community the event is FREE for pre-registered visitors.</p> <p>More than 36 speakers took part in CropTec 2016 and together with over 140 exhibitors and organizations helped clarify some of the uncertainty and demonstrated how technical excellence could help improve growers' competitive edge and profitability. Most of the seminars were standing room only. The programme focused on four key technical areas affecting profitability – crop establishment, crop nutrition, crop protection and crop breeding, featuring some of the industry's most acknowledged experts. Proving CropTec lives up to its reputation as the knowledge exchange event for progressive arable farmers and their advisers.</p>
Target public	Farmers, advisers
Contact details	http://www.croptecshow.com/index.php/contact-us

LAMMA'18

Name	LAMMA'18
Website address	http://www.lammashow.com/
Type of event.	Fair
Date	17 th and 18th January 2018
Place	Peterborough, United Kingdom
Description	LAMMA the UK's largest farm machinery, equipment and agricultural services show is

	FREE to attend with no requirement to register before the event. LAMMA takes place whatever the weather.
Target public	
Contact details	http://www.lammashow.com/page.cfm/Link=8/t=m/goSection=6

Agri-Tech Week and REAP Conference

Name	Agri-Tech Week and REAP Conference
Website address	http://www.agritech-east.co.uk/events/agri-tech-east-events-2017/
Type of event.	Conference
Date	6-10th November 2017, REAP Conference 9th November
Place	REAP Conference, Cambridge and various locations
Description	To celebrate innovation across the region we have a week of agri-tech events with something to interest everyone. Agri-Tech Week is a partnership initiative to showcase excellence in innovation across the agri-tech value chain, brokering links and fostering new relationships between businesses, researchers and government. Agri-Tech Week also provides an opportunity to welcome new collaborators, customers and partners to the east of England's agri-tech ecosystem, and features events, visits, workshops and discussions across the east of England, as well as Agri-Tech East's annual REAP Conference in Cambridge
Target public	
Contact details	http://www.agritech-east.co.uk/contact/

7.2.5 Greece

AGROTHESSALY

Name	Agrothessaly
Website address	http://agrothessaly.helexpo.gr/en
Type of event.	Fair
Date	from 9 th to 12 th of March 2017
Place	Neapoli Larissa
Description	AGROTHESSALY (11 th Pan-Hellenic Fair for Agriculture and Livestock) is an Agricultural-Livestock-Environmental Fair that has been organised for 20 years in Larissa, in the heartland of Greece, as a continuation of the already successful Fair, aiming at upgrading it into the largest regional exhibition of the sector.
Target public	
Contact details	agrothessaly@helexpo.gr

AGROTICA

Agrotica

Name	Agrotica
Website address	http://www.helexpo.gr/en
Type of event.	Fair
Date	from 1 st to 4 th of February 2018
Place	Thessaloniki Fair
Description	Agrotica in Thessaloniki is an international exhibition for agricultural machinery, equipment and material, and one of the largest fairs of its kind in the world. At their meeting national and international representatives of the industry can learn about the newest machines, accessories and other products. On this important trade fair visitors can see the latest achievements of technology and science for the agricultural sector.
Target public	
Contact details	agrotica@helexpo.gr

7.2.6 Serbia

Novi Sad Fair

Name	International Agricultural Fair
Website address	http://www.sajam.net/live/Events/Fairs/2017/84th+International+Agricultural+Fair
Type of event.	Fair
Date	from 13 st to 19 th of May 2017
Place	Novi Sad Fair
Description	International Agricultural Fair is a 7 day event being held from 13th May to 19th May 2017 at the Novi Sad Fair in Novi Sad, Serbia. This event showcases product from Agriculture & Forestry industry. The show will be arranged to collect information necessary for resolving the current issues pertaining in the agricultural sector. In the International Agricultural Fair various concepts will be discussed such as Machines and equipment for forest management; Civil engineering in agriculture and food industry; Machines and equipment for animal feed preparation and processing; Machines for packing material; Agricultural machinery and spare parts, etc.
Target public	
Contact details	info@sajam.net

7.2.7 Netherlands

Potato Europe

Name	Potato Europe, theme 2017
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Website address	http://www.potatoeurope.nl/
Type of event.	
Date	13 th and 14 th of September 2017
Place	Emmeloord,
Description	<p>Potato Europe is an annual event for the European potato industry, organised in rotation in either Germany, Belgium, France or the Netherlands. Potato Europe 2017 will be held in Emmeloord, the potato capital of the Netherlands</p> <p>The theme of this year's edition – 'Potatoes feed & meet the world' – is linked to the potato's huge potential to feed the world's growing population. In addition, PotatoEurope in 2017 is the leading platform for the exchange of information related to precision farming for potatoes.</p>
Target public	
Contact details	p.hoftijzer@dlg.org

smartAKIS
Smart Farming Thematic Network

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